

ROBOTS AND AUTONOMOUS DEVICES IN AGRICULTURE

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Abstract. *The article examines the integration of robotic and autonomous technologies in agriculture, focusing on their potential to revolutionize traditional farming practices. It describes the diverse designs of robotic machines currently being developed through collaborations between major manufacturers and small innovative firms. The article outlines six key stages of automation, highlighting how machines evolve from manual control to full autonomy. Emphasizing the importance of these advancements, the author suggests that the future of agricultural machinery will enable farmers to manage resources more effectively, thus addressing pressing challenges like efficiency and labor shortages.*

Keywords: *robot, autonomous device, autonomous agricultural machine, autonomous tractor.*

Today, the agricultural sector is reaching a new level with the integration of digital technologies and automation processes. Global challenges such as ensuring food security, increasing efficiency, and overcoming labor shortages are driving the need for modern technologies. In particular, robots and autonomous devices are fundamentally transforming traditional processes in agriculture, giving farmers the opportunity to manage resources more efficiently and effectively. This article examines the current role of robotic and autonomous technologies in agriculture, their prospects, and emerging innovations in this field.

In the future, robotic machines in agriculture will perform their tasks independently according to program management, under the control of a remote control center. At the prototype level, the designs of robotic machines are highly diverse. Large agricultural machinery factories, in collaboration with innovative small companies, are developing robots and autonomous devices suitable for mass production.

Robots are automatically controlled, reprogrammable devices capable of movement along three or more axes and versatile functionality. Robots can be stationary, fixed in place, or mobile, moving devices. Autonomous devices are land-based vehicles and machines that do not require a driver or operator and are not controlled remotely, but if necessary, human control can be resumed.

Figure 1. Fendt Xavier small agricultural robot

a- traditional control, b- precision agriculture technology, c- coordination and optimization between machines, d- real-time machine automation, e- supervised autonomy, f- full autonomy, robotics

The automation of agricultural machines began with the use of autonomous devices. The main stages of automation are as follows:

1. **Traditional control:** The machine lacks autonomy and is manually controlled by a person.
2. **Precision agriculture technology:** The machine has simple autonomous technological systems (automatic control, row management, adjusting the working machine based on soil properties), and all technologies operate independently.
3. **Coordination and optimization between machines:** Machines can communicate with each other and can be used to coordinate and synchronize tasks between machines, for example, a single tractor driver can manage multiple machines.
4. **Real-time machine automation:** Machine control is automatic based on current environmental conditions and other parameters, but technology governs the machine, such as selecting speed according to soil conditions or planning routes based on centralized logistics instructions.
5. **Supervised autonomy:** A smart tractor or smart machine performs tasks independently (a combine manages a tractor pulling a trailer during harvest), but machines are still visible to the operator from a distance, linking the stands to a remote logistics center in turn.
6. **Full autonomy, robotics:** In the future of agriculture, machines will perform their tasks independently according to their programmed control under the supervision of a remote control center [1].

Below are several examples of robotic and autonomous agricultural machines.

Figure 2. Bear Flag Robotics autonomous tractor

Figure 3. First prototype of an autonomous MTZ tractor

It is not necessary to purchase a completely new tractor to have an autonomous tractor. The Canadian company Bear Flag Robotics is developing a control system that can be used to retrofit existing modern agricultural tractors (Figure 2). A tractor equipped with Bear Flag Robotics' control system has self-driving capabilities, and its software can be installed in a short time. If the crop field and routes are mapped using a smart tractor, data can be transferred to the operation of other machines in the fleet. The automated route generator can adapt to obstacles such as unique land boundaries, roads, waterways, and power lines. The responsible person can monitor the independently operating agricultural machinery fleet entrusted to them from anywhere through the farm's personal communication user interfaces. Operators can receive real-time information about the operation of the tractors. The autonomous tractor is also capable of operating at high speeds with existing agricultural machinery. The Bear Flag Robotics system can be customized for many machines. In addition to real-time telemetry, users can also access 360° live video feeds, allowing operators to take immediate control of the machine at the press of a button if a problem or need for intervention arises [2].

Figure 4. Automated version of the Vermeer ZR5-1200 self-driving round baler

Autonomous Belarus Tractor: The driverless MTZ 3523i tractor is based on a diesel-electric hybrid power transmission and transmission system. It has been replaced by a smart control system managed by a computer programmed with driver cameras, sensors, and GPS location detection modules. The power source of the autonomous tractor is a 350-horsepower Cummins diesel engine, which provides two speed ranges through a gear system without mechanical gears: 0-15 km/h and 0-50 km/h. Initial operational tests in the field were carried out using a three-section mower and an 8-blade rotary plow [3].

Figure 5. Mechanism for acquiring the Vermeer "Bale Hawk" autonomous machine

The American company Vermeer is successfully implementing innovative work in the field of hay and forage management. For example, in 2017, it introduced the world's first self-driving round baler, designated model ZR5-1200. The machine is equipped with a Cummins diesel engine with 173 horsepower and uses Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) sensors for line tracking and automatic machine control. The 6000 kg Bale Hawk features a rubber belt and is equipped with a Deutz diesel engine. This machine can pick up and transport three bales sequentially (Figure 6) [3].

Figure 6. Vermeer «Bale Hawk» autonomous machine for processing three round bales

Robot tractors are being produced in several copies using components from the Yanmar YT4/5 tractor series (with diesel engines ranging from 63 to 113 horsepower). The YT4/5A family of autonomous tractors represents Yanmar's «Smart Robot Driver» self-driving agricultural machinery. These robot tractors can navigate accurately and safely along pre-programmed routes using available tools in rural areas. Machines equipped with Continuously Variable Transmission (CVT) can be operated at very low traction speeds. The tractors can also work in groups under close inspector supervision [4].

Figure 7. Yanmar YT5113A autonomous tractor

The SMASH data collection system consists of a four-wheeled, electrically controlled, and four-wheel-driven robotic mobile base, equipped with manipulators and vision systems, as well as drones and an additional underground station. The system monitors and inspects plants, collects soil samples for analysis, and determines the necessary amounts of agricultural chemicals for

precise application. The SMASH prototype is currently engaged in collecting and presenting data on grape and spinach plantations.

**Figure 8. Yanmar SMASH data collection
robotic system**

**Figure 9. OMNiPOWER innovative
universal robot tool carrier**

Raven Industries, Inc. is poised to play a leading role in the future of agricultural mechanization. Raven™ offers products for precision agriculture, autonomous machinery, robotic machine control, field computers, software controls, GPS control systems, wireless communication systems, cloud-based data management, and logistics technologies. OMNiPOWER is Raven’s new universal robotic tool carrier (Figure 9) [5]. It enables the performance of various agricultural tasks, such as planting, spraying, fertilizing, and more, using easily interchangeable smart agricultural machines. The hydraulic four-wheeled machine is equipped with a 4.5-liter, 173 horsepower turbocharged Cummins diesel engine. The chassis tool carrier can optionally move laterally and longitudinally, as well as forward and backward (Figures 10 and 11).

Farmers can control the autonomous machine through a wireless remote control or a tablet connected to a mobile network. The pre-defined route plan uploaded to the control unit is executed by the machine using GPS. Raven’s «Perception» optical and avoidance system employs multiple cameras and radars to navigate around people, animals, and other obstacles, ensuring the task are performed safely. Smart agricultural machines (such as seeders, fertilizer spreaders, sprayers, etc.) have been developed for the robotic tool carrier [6].

Figure 10. Smart seeder OMNiPOWER robotic tool carrier

Figure 11. Smart sprayer OMNiPOWER robotic tool carrier

The AgBot, a robot tractor developed by the Dutch company AgXeed BV, is powered by a 156 horsepower (115 kW) Deutz diesel engine. It is controlled via an electric drive chain powered by a rubber-belt engine and a 700 V voltage electric generator, allowing it to reach a maximum speed of 13.5 km/h. The tractor features a GPS system, sensors, and optical obstacle detection, with its working width adjustable infinitely from 1.8 to 3 meters. The front and rear hitch capacities are 3 and 8 tons, respectively, and the hydraulic system’s pump delivers a flow rate of 80 liters per minute. The maximum output of the electric motor-driven PTO is 100 kW. During transport, implements can be collected manually on top of the autonomous vehicle.

Figure 12. AgBot robotic tractor developed by AgXeed BV

Figure 13. VITIROVER solar robotic lawn mower

The robotic machine for ecological weed removal from lawns, produced by the French company Vitirover (Figure 13), is a small robot with a length of 750 mm, a width of 390 mm, a height of 290 mm, and a weight of 20 kg. It is driven by four-wheel hub electric motors, allowing it to reach a maximum speed of 300 m/h. The electrical energy is primarily supplied by a solar panel located on top of the robot, and secondarily by a battery. The front of the machine features an electric motor that drives 2 or 3 rotating cutting blades, achieving a cutting width of 30 cm and a cutting height of 3-10 cm. The machine autonomously navigates within the boundary of the programmed area using a GNSS satellite positioning system, detecting and avoiding obstacles. Up to 50 robots can be controlled by a supervisor, who can intervene in their operations through a mobile network within a 20 km radius. In addition to the regular operation of the robots, the use of chemical herbicides can be avoided in large grassy areas (such as vineyards, orchards, and others) [7].

Orio is a multifunctional, autonomous, high-precision robot designed for vegetable cultivation operations. The robot is 100% electric, helping producers reduce their environmental impact.

Figure 14. Orio

«Orio provides a sustainable alternative to using herbicides, protecting the soil, improving labor conditions, and collecting data for smart farming». «Orio offers a sustainable, practical, and intelligent farming

solution that integrates advanced technologies. Unique artificial intelligence, directed by years of experience across several hectares, allows us to ensure the quality and reliability of the farming tasks performed by the robot».

Orio is based on GPS and camera systems, facilitating maneuverability around agricultural lands. The robot is equipped with multiple sensors that operate based on artificial intelligence algorithms, specifically designed for high-precision weed control. The implements attached to the center of the robot are controlled through integrated technology, ensuring optimal accuracy [8].

Conclusion

Based on the above analysis, the introduction of robots and autonomous devices in agriculture significantly enhances the efficiency and sustainability of the sector. These technologies play a crucial role in optimizing processes ranging from planting crops to harvesting and managing resources. Nevertheless, the successful application of these technologies depends on addressing technical and economic challenges, as well as effectively preparing farmers to adapt to new systems. Therefore, the future development in this field will be closely linked to the broader implementation of innovative solutions, the formulation of policies supporting technological changes, and the training of skilled specialists to work with robotics and autonomous devices.

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